

COGNITIVE APPROACHES: FIGURE AND GROUND OF "HOUSE MADE OF DAWN" BY N. SCOTT MOMADAY

Imomova Sayyora Sayfiddin qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19106608>

Abstract

This article analyses the use of figure and ground relationships in the novel *House Made of Dawn* from the perspective of cognitive poetics. The study examines how N. Scott Momaday organises the reader's attention through his literary style. In traditional Western literature, human characters and their actions are usually central, while nature serves as the background. However, in this novel, the author often alters this conventional structure: landscape, nature, dawn, land, and space are depicted as primary figures, whereas humans appear as part of the background or environment. During the study, sections of the novel, including the prologue, "The Longhair", "The Priest of the Sun", and "The Dawn Runner", are analysed. As a result, this method of depiction by the author serves not only as an aesthetic device but also as an important cognitive mechanism expressing the worldview of Native Americans – the idea of harmony between humans, nature, and culture.

Key words: figure, ground, indigenous identity, healing, active, background.

Introduction.

N. Scott Momaday Native American writer, poet, and novelist, was born in 1934. He is deeply connected to the Kiowa heritage. He grew up in America, and therefore storytelling strongly influenced his writing. Momaday's work is famous for its mixing of oral tradition, myth, and modern literary technique. In his writing, we can see the power of language, spiritual survival, and identity. One of the books that reflects the history of Natives is *House Made of Dawn*. He even got a Pulitzer Prize for *House Made of Dawn*. This book is about Indigenous identity, trauma, healing, and cultural survival in modern life.

House Made of Dawn is about Abel, who returns to his home after World War II. He is a young Native American man who struggles with disconnection, silence, violence, and alcoholism instead of recovering after coming home. For Abel, living in modern America and his traditional Native environment is difficult. The novel is narrated nonlinearly, and it shifts between memories, making reading challenging. The main themes of the novel are identity crisis, cultural dislocation, violence, and healing. The title is taken from a Navajo chant and symbolizes the relationship between humans and nature. This novel requires readers to make sense. It is ideal for stylistic analysis. Cognitive approaches are useful in explaining the figure and ground, prototypes and reading. Through these cognitive models, we can observe how the language and structure used by Momaday recreate the experience of disorientation in Abel and his subsequent slow shift into meaning and harmony

Main body.

The figure and ground.

The figure and ground theory explains how a literary text organizes the reader's attention. The figure is the most clearly visible element in perception, and the ground is the background that supports the figure and gives it meaning. In many Western literary works, human characters, their actions, thoughts, or dialogues are usually the focus, while the place and nature remain as the background. However, in the novel *House Made of Dawn*, N. Scott Momaday

reverses this traditional structure in many cases. Instead of putting human images at the center, he brings the natural environment to the fore. The landscape, the weather, the dawn, the mesa, the river, and the physical space become the main focus, while the person is depicted as small, silent, and sometimes absorbed into the environment. This is not just an artistic style, but also expresses a worldview in which place is closely blended with personality, culture, and meaning. A clear example of this is found in the Prologue section of the novel. The work begins not with Abel's thoughts or dialogues, but with a depiction of the earth.

"The land was very old and everlasting... The land was still and strong. It was beautiful all around."

Only then does Abel appear, and he is also depicted in a very small and helpless state:

"Against the winter sky and the long, light landscape of the valley at dawn, he seemed almost to be standing still, very little and alone."

Here, the earth acts as a figure, and Abel as a background. Cognitively, the reader's attention is primarily focused on the stability and power of space, not on the person. Abel is depicted as lost in nature. This shows from the beginning of the novel that meaning is born not from human actions, but from the relationship with space.

A similar figure-background relationship is observed in Part I: "The Longhair" (July 20). When Abel returns to Walatowo after the war, the chapter begins with a description of the river valley:

"The river lies in a valley of hills and fields... The sun strikes the canyon floor only a few hours each day."

Here, Abel's inner experiences are not directly expressed. Instead, space, light, and geography come to the fore. Abel is present, but not at the center. The ground, not the background, becomes the cognitive center. As a result, the reader understands Abel's state of mind not through direct way, but through the environment.

The relationship between figure and ground changes dramatically in Part II: The Priest of the Sun (Los Angeles, 1952). Here, the urban environment remains the main background. For example, the city is described as follows:

"The basement was cold and dreary... The walls were bare and gray and streaked with water. The air was heavy and stale."

In these passages, Abel's identity disappears, and he falls into a repetitive life. The city does not suit Abel, it does not support him culturally or cognitively. The reader feels Abel's alienation not through explanations, but through the setting itself.

At the end of the novel, the final section "**The Dawn Runner**", it is mentioned, *"He was running, and under his breath he began to sing."* In this final scene, Abel is a figure, but he is no longer separated from the background (the environment). His movement, his running is in harmony with the earth and the time of day, the dawn. Unlike in the earlier parts of the novel, the environment does not overwhelm him, and he does not disappear into silence. On the contrary, the figure is Abel and the backgrounds are the earth, the dawn, and the rhythm which work together. Abel is figure not separated from the ground. Through culture, storytelling, and ceremonies, and through this, the author shows that harmony between man and the world is the main path to healing.

Conclusion.

Momaday's narrative style is not simply chosen to be "difficult" or complex; rather, the form of the text actively guides the reader's experience. Through the relationship of figure and ground, the novel focuses on the land, the silence, and the environment, and often reduces the centrality of the human protagonist. This reflects an Indigenous worldview. As a result, the reader begins to see Abel not only as a person with psychological problems, but also within a larger context with cultural and spatial meaning.

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